

Effects of Daily Life Behavior with a Secondary Task on Performance and Psychophysiological States

Masahiro Seo, Kent Nagumo, Kosuke Oiwa and Akio Nozawa

Abstract: The objective of this study was to evaluate the effect of daily life behavior with a secondary task on performance and psychophysiological states. The experiments were based on two conditions: dishwashing (Control) only, and dishwashing while listening to favorite music (Favorite). In the present study, statistical evaluation was conducted to assess the performance and psychophysiological states between the Control and Favorite conditions. As a result, the electromyogram of the ulnar flexor muscle of the wrist in the dominant hand, which is a performance index, showed significant differences between the two conditions. The R-R Interval, which is the physiological index, showed no significant differences between the two conditions. Additionally, the impression of the feelings, which is the psychological index in the Favorite condition were higher than those in the Control condition. Therefore, it is suggested that there is a psychological change as a primary effect of listening to favorite music during daily life behavior, and the performance may be improved as a secondary effect of the psychological change. In conclusion, listening to favorite music decreased the mental fatigue, which is associated with the subjective feelings.

Keywords: Daily life behavior; Multitasking; Psychophysiological measurement; Stress structure

I. INTRODUCTION

In modern society, stress factors associated with daily life behavior have been increasing. These factors are the major causes of anxiety and depression in women [1][2]. Evaluation of conditions during daily life behavior is essential for reducing the number of patients of anxiety and depression caused by stress factors of daily life behavior.

Conventional methods for evaluating conditions during daily life behavior have been performed by interviewing or using psychological assessments, such as the Beck Depression Inventory-II [3] and State-Trait Anxiety Inventory [4]. On the other hand, methods for evaluating stress factors caused by daily life behavior have also been performed. Stress factors are mainly caused by fatigue, which is broadly classified into physical and mental fatigue [5]. Mainly, studies on mental fatigue have been performed owing to increasing human error and health disorders caused by mental works in the information society. However, no studies that consider physical and mental fatigue have

been conducted so far, and it is necessary to consider physical fatigue when considering the fatigue related to daily life behavior. Thus, we hypothesized that these types of fatigue are contained in a single stress structure. Our previous study has clarified the stress structure based on the psychophysiological indices measured during multitasking. Multitasking consisted of daily life behavior (the primary task) and a secondary task. The mental fatigue of the secondary task was altered in order to reveal the stress structure during multitasking by changing the internal state of the stress structure. We compared the psychophysiological states between the single task and the multitasking. The psychophysiological indices between the single task and the multitasking were found to be different. As a result, it was suggested that a mental reserve ability called spare capacity, [6] should be incorporated in the stress structure. Additionally, it was suggested that the impression of the secondary task was captured as overall task impression [7].

On the other hand, the stress structure is expected to change with the contents of the secondary task in

Corresponding Author: Akio Nozawa. Department of Science and Engineering, Aoyama Gakuin University, 5-10-1 Fuchinobe, Chuo-ku, Sagamihara-shi, Kanagawa, 252-0206, Japan, Tel: +8142-759-6419, Fax: +81-42-759-6528, E-mail: akio@ee.aoyama.ac.jp

multitasking. Listening to music, in particular, is expected to relieve stress and improve performance [8][9]. Thus, the stress structure is expected to be altered by the contents of the secondary task.

The objective of this study was to evaluate the effect of daily life behavior with a secondary task on performance and psychophysiological states. In the present study, statistical evaluation was conducted to study the influence of listening to favorite music during daily life behavior on performance and psychophysiological states. Dishwashing was used as daily life behavior and the listening to favorite music was added a secondary task.

II. EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

A. Experimental system

In this present study, a dishwashing task was performed to simulate daily life behavior. The experimental system consisted of a sink, a heart rate variability (HRV) recorder (eMotion FAROS 90°, Mega Electronics Ltd, Finland), and a piece of wireless biological measuring equipment (Polymate Mini AP108, TEAC Co., Tokyo, Japan). The experiments were conducted with the subjects in an upright position. The sink for the dishwashing task was 400mm in length, 600mm in width, 800mm in height, and 160mm in depth. To create dirty tableware, they were stained with an aqueous pen. The experiments started 15minutes after the subjects entered the experiment room to ensure that the subjects were accustomed to the room temperature. The HRV recorder was attached according to the modified lead II scheme. The HRV recorder recorded a time series of R-R Interval (RRI), which represents the heart period by using built-in data storage. The electromyogram (EMG), a wireless biological measuring equipment, with a sampling frequency of 500Hz was used. The ulnar flexor muscle of the wrist in the dominant hand was measured as the target muscle that acts on the dorsiflexion of the wrist joint.

Different psychophysiological and performance indices were measured. The RRI was extracted from the heart rate variability recorder. The index represented an autonomic nervous system activity. The EMG of the ulnar flexor muscle of the wrist of the dominant hand was used as a performance index. The impression of the feelings was evaluated using the visual analog scale (VAS), classifying the perception as Comfort, Awareness, and Vigorous. The impression of the feelings was used as a psychological index to assess the subjective feelings.

B. Procedure and conditions

Five healthy adult males and two adult females aged 21-23 years were included in the study. The subjects were fully informed about the experiments and the objectives of this study before confirming their participation. The number of experiments per subject was once a day. The experiments were carried out in an experiment room (Room temperature of $25.6 \pm 0.3^{\circ}\text{C}$). The experiment protocol consisted of a 2-minute resting segment (Rest1), a segment with the dishwashing tasks, and a 3-minute resting segment. The dishwashing activity consisted of “wash,” “rinse,” and “wipe” segments. This protocol was conducted two times. The order of dishwashing tasks was counterbalanced across the subjects. Additionally, the dishwashing method was not specified. The experiments were conducted under two the conditions that included only dishwashing (Control) and dishwashing while listening to favorite music (Favorite). Before the experiment, the subjects’ preferences were surveyed, and their favorite music was selected.

C. Indices for analysis

The RRI was measured as an index of autonomic nervous system activity. The shortening of the RRI reflects increased activation of the sympathetic nervous system or decreased activation of the parasympathetic nervous system. The RRI was normalized based on the average value during the Rest1. The EMG was measured as an index of the amount of muscle activity during dishwashing. An integrated EMG per segment was calculated from the measured time series of the EMG. Normalization of the EMG signal amplitude is required when attempting to compare the signals from different subjects. One simple normalization method is to make an individual recording from each muscle when the subject is attempting to attain the general maximum contraction for the individual muscle. The type of EMG signal normalization is called Maximum Voluntary Contraction (MVC) Normalization [10]. In this study, maximum muscle per second was extracted, divided, and normalized to obtain Maximum Voluntary Contraction. The VAS is a method for subjectively evaluating a mental state, by asking a subject to select a portion on a line, with a pair of adjectives set at the ends. The VAS was used as a psychological index, to assess the subjective feelings. For this study, the assessment items were Comfort, Awareness, and Vigorous and they were defined by lines using the adjective pairs displeasure-pleasure, sleepy-awake, and tired-sprightly, respectively. The minimum-maximum values of the

VAS score were normalized to 0-1.

III. ANALYSIS METHODS

In the present study, statistical evaluation was conducted to compare the performance and psychophysiological states between the Control and Favorite conditions. Since the task time differed for each subject, evaluation segments of the RRI were defined as 30 seconds after the start, 30 seconds before the end of the “wash,” “rinse,” and “wipe” segments, and 60 seconds after the end of the task for each case. Evaluation segments of the EMG were defined as the segments of “wash,” “rinse,” and “wipe”. The averages in each segment were used as the evaluation value. The Wilcoxon signed-rank test (** : $p < 0.01$, * : $p < 0.05$, + : $p < 0.1$) was used to compare the baseline for the RRI, and to compare the central values of the EMG and the VAS scores for each condition. Data of the EMG, the RRI, and the NST were subjected to a two-way repeated measures analysis of variance (ANOVA) to reveal whether the differences in the data between the two conditions (Control and Favorite) and the time-laps were statistically significant.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Performance evaluation

Figure 1 shows the normalized EMG values in the dominant hand for each segment. The horizontal axis indicates the elements of each segment. The vertical axis indicates the value of EMG data. From the results of the Wilcoxon signed-rank test, a significant difference between the two conditions was found in the “wipe” segment ($p < 0.05$). From the results of the ANOVA, the significant effects of conditions ($F(1,41) = 15.1, p < 0.01$) and time-laps ($F(2,41) = 7.35, p < 0.01$), and significant interaction between the conditions and the time-laps ($F(2,41) = 3.60, p < 0.1$) were found for the EMG.

The EMG values represent the performance that showed significant differences between the two conditions. It is suggested that the performance was improved in the Favorite condition when compared to the Control condition. In other words, performance is likely to be influenced by listening to favorite music.

Figure 1. The maximum voluntary contraction obtained from the normalized EMG values in the dominant hand (N=7). The error bars represent the standard error

Figure 2. The average value of RRI (N=7). The error bars represent the standard error.

B. Physiological evaluation

Figure 2 shows the average values of RRI in each segment. The horizontal axis indicates each segment per element. The vertical axis indicates the values of the RRI data. The baseline indicates the average value of Rest1 for each subject. From the results of the Wilcoxon signed-rank test, significant differences between baseline and the average values of the RRI are observed. From the results of ANOVA, significant effect of time-lapse ($F(9,139) = 10.2, p < 0.01$) was found for the RRI. There were no significant effects of conditions ($F(1,139) = 1.32, p > 0.1$), as well as no significant interaction between the conditions and time-lapse ($F(9,139) = 2.42, p > 0.1$). Since the RRI was decreasing from the baseline, it was deduced that sympathetic nervous system activity was increased during dishwashing.

From the results of ANOVA, the main effect was found in time-laps. Hence the result of RRI was decreased with increasing stress due to the time-laps. From the results of the RRI, it is evident that the physiological states are not influenced by listening to favorite music.

C. Psychological evaluation

Figure 3 shows the deferential values of the VAS scores. The horizontal axis indicates each assessment item of the subjective feelings. The vertical axis indicates the deferential values of VAS scores. From the results of the Wilcoxon signed-rank test, significant differences in the baseline and average VAS scores between the two conditions were observed. The Awareness value increased significantly ($p < 0.05$) in the Favorite condition. Nonetheless, there were no significant differences in the VAS sores were found between the two conditions.

The results of the subjective feelings showed no significant differences between the two conditions. On the other hand, all the assessment items of the VAS in the Favorite condition were higher than those in the Control condition. In other words, psychological states are likely to be influenced by listening to favorite music.

The results indicate that the subjective feelings represent the impression of the tasks. Hence, it suggested that there is a psychological change as a primary effect of listening to favorite music during daily life behavior. The EMG values represent the performance by depicting the significant differences in the “wipe” segment between the two conditions. It is suggested that the performance was improved in the

Favorite condition when compared to the Control condition. It can be suggested that the performance may have improved as a secondary effect of the psychological change. Since a significant difference was found in the “wipe” segment at the end of the task, it is thought that the performance improves as a secondary effect.

We hypothesized that the stress structure consists of physical fatigue, mental fatigue, and spare capacity. In the present study, psychological change and improved performance were observed while listening to favorite music during the tasks. Hence it is suggested that listening to favorite music decreased the mental fatigue in the stress structure, which is associated with the subjective feelings.

Figure 3. The deferential values of VAS scores (N=7). The error bars represent the standard error.

V. CONCLUSION

The objective of this study was to evaluate the effect of daily life behavior with secondary task on performance and psychophysiological states. The experiments were performed under two conditions (Control and Favorite). In the present study, statistical evaluation was conducted to compare the performance and the psychophysiological states between the Control and Favorite conditions. The EMG evaluation showed significant differences between the two conditions. The RRI evaluation showed no significant differences between the two conditions. While the VAS scores in all the assessment items were higher in the Favorite condition than those in the Control condition. Therefore, it is suggested that there is a psychological change as a primary effect of listening to favorite music during daily life behavior and the performance may be improved as a secondary effect of the psychological change. In conclusion, listening to favorite music decreased the mental fatigue in the stress structure, which is associated with the subjective feelings.

REFERENCES

- [1] L. B. Fan, J. A. Blumenthal, L. L. Watkins, and A. Sherwood. Work and home stress: associations with anxiety and depression symptoms Occupational Medicine. (Lond), Vol. 65, No. 2, pp. 110-116, 2015.
- [2] A. Hoshino, S. Amano, K. Suzuki, and M. Suwa, “Relationships between depression and stress factors in housework and paid work among Japanese women,” Hong Kong Journal Occupational Therapy, Vol. 27, No. 1, pp. 35-41, 2016.
- [3] A. T. Beck, R. A. Steer and M. G. Carbin. Psychometric

- properties of the Beck Depression Inventory: Twenty-five years of evaluation. *Clinical Psychology Re-view*, Vol.8, No.1, pp. 77-100, 1998
- [4] P. A. Patel, P. P. Patel, and A. V. Khadilkar, et al. Impact of occupation on stress and anxiety among Indian women. *Women & Health*, Vol.57, No.3, pp. 392-401, 2017
- [5] T. Chalder, G. Berelowitz, and T. Pawlikowska, et al. Development of a fatigue scale. *Journal of Psychosomatic Research* Vol. 37, No. 2, pp. 147-153, 1993
- [6] K. Suda, T. Hirai, and O. Saijo, A study of spare capacity on motor learning. The 42nd Conference of the Japanese Society of Physiological Education, Health and Sports Sciences, 0310506 (in Japanese) 1991
- [7] M. Seo, K. Oiwa, and A. Nozawa. The analysis of the stress structure with sub-task in housework behavior. The 13th spring conference JSKE, WE1-4 (in Japanese) 2018
- [8] P. C. Terry, C. I. Karageorghis, A. M. Saha, and S. D'Auria. Effects of synchronous music on treadmill running among elite triathletes. *Journal of Science Medicine and Sport*. Vol. 15, no. 1, pp. 52-57, 2012
- [9] M. Bigliassi, C. I. Karageorghis, D. T. Bishop, A. V. Nowicky, and M. J. Wright. Cerebral effects of music during isometric exercise: An fMRI study. *International Journal of Psychophysiology*. Vol. 133, pp. 131-139, 2018
- [10] V. T. Inman, H.J. Ralston, and J. B. De C. M. Saunders, et al. Relation of human electromyogram to muscular tension. *Electroencephalography and Clinical Neurophysiology*, Vol. 4, No. 2, pp. 187-194, 1952